

Synthesis and structural characterization of mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with 1,8-diaminonaphthalene and 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate

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Abstract : Mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} with 1,8-diaminonaphthalene (dan) and 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate {CED²⁻ = [S₂C=C(COOC₂H₅)(CN)]²⁻} of the compositions [Ni(dan)₂(CED)] and [Ni(dan)₃](CED) have been synthesised. The complex, [Ni(dan)₂(CED)] was allowed to react with pyridine, α-, β- or γ-picoline which yielded product of the composition, [Ni(dan)(CED)L₂].xH₂O [L = pyridine (py), x = 8; α-picoline (α-pic), x = 2; β-picoline (β-pic), x = 2 and γ-picoline (γ-pic), x = 8]. The synthesised complexes were characterised by analytical data, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, electronic and infrared spectral studies. The molar conductance data in DMF solution suggest non-electrolytic nature of the complexes except [Ni(dan)₃](CED) whose value suggest 1 : 1 electrolytic nature. The magnetic and electronic spectral studies indicate distorted octahedral coordination around Ni^{II} ion in these complexes. The infrared spectral study suggest bi-dentate chelating behaviour of dan and CED²⁻ ion while mono-dentate behaviours of py, α-, β- and γ-picolines.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complex, 1,8-diaminonaphthalene, 1,1-dithiolate, nickel(II).

Introduction

Dithiolate ligands among sulphur donors have attracted the coordination chemists by virtue of its chelating as well as bridging behaviours in non-transition as well as transition metals complexes. It has remained area of interest for several decades^{1,2} and recently due to electrically conducting molecular solids³⁻⁶. The dithiolate class of ligands have got attention of coordination chemists also from various reasons such as stabilization of square planar geometry around transition metal ions, stabilization of transition metals in its unusual oxidation states, facile redox behaviour, interesting magnetic and spectral properties, in catalysis, model for active sites of many enzyme systems, magnetic exchange behaviour, electron transfer reactions, industrial and biological applications⁷⁻¹⁵. The sulphur ligand, 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate, considered here belongs to general class of 1,1-dithiolates and shows interesting coordination properties by virtue of its chelating and bridging behaviours which have been found in its binary, ternary and hetero-bimetallic complexes^{1,2,16-19}.

On the other hand, aromatic diamines have also been centre for attraction for coordination chemists in synthesizing transition as well as non transition metal complexes. However, these diamines have greatly been used in synthesis of Schiff bases used as ligands. 1,8-Diaminonaphthalene is one of aromatic diamines which has been used in synthesis of a few number of transition metal complexes²⁰⁻²³. While its Schiff bases obtained from condensation with a variety of aldehydes and ketones have been used for complexation with a variety of transition metal ions²⁴⁻³². The complexes have found various applications such as in polymerisation²⁵, as antioxidant³⁰ and as antimicrobial agents³². A conducting polymer of copper with 1,8-diaminonaphthalene has been used for electro-catalytic reduction of oxygen³³. The nickel(II) complexes arising from 1,8-diaminonaphthalene have also found application in hydrogenation of acetophenone in place of complexes of precious metals such as Ru, Rh and Ir³⁴. Films of poly(1,8-diaminonaphthalene) and poly(metal-1,8-diaminonaphthalene) have been synthesised and used in electro-catalytic reduction of molecular oxygen^{35,36}.

The literature survey reveals that there is no report on mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with 1,8-diaminonaphthalene and 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate. Thus, it was thought of interest to undertake the synthesis and structural characterization of mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with these two ligands and their reactivity study towards heterocyclic nitrogen donors such as pyridine, α -, β - or γ -picoline. The results of our investigations are reported in this communication.

Results and discussion

The analytical data and stoichiometry of the synthesized complexes reveal the formation of mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) of the compositions, $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_3(\text{CED})]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})(\text{CED})\text{L}_2] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [L = pyridine (py), $x = 8$; α -picoline (α -pic), $x = 2$; β -picoline (β -pic), $x = 2$ and γ -picoline (γ -pic), $x = 8$; dan = 1,8-diaminonaphthalene; CED^{2-} = 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate]. The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are soluble in coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. The complexes, $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_3(\text{CED})]$ show decomposition temperature 176 and 160 °C while rest of complexes do not show decomposition upto 300 °C. The content of water molecules were determined by estimating weight loss after heating the compounds in an electric oven in the temperature range 110–180 °C. The weight loss experiments suggested that the weight loss occurred in the temperature range 110–120 °C indicating that they are held in the lattice of the complexes. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMF (10^{-3} M) solution suggest non-electrolytic nature of the complexes except the complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_3(\text{CED})]$ which shows 1 : 1 electrolytic nature in solution³⁷.

Magnetic moment :

All the complexes except $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$ show magnetic moment values in the range 2.87–3.11 B.M. suggesting paramagnetism corresponding to two unpaired electrons. The complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$, shows sub-normal magnetic moment value 2.47 B.M. which is slightly lower than the octahedral complexes of Ni^{II} . When non-equivalent ligands are present in a complex then they cause distortion which leads to deviation from octahedral geometry and possibility of configurational equilibrium arises. This causes lowering of magnetic moment value

for a complex. The sub-normal magnetic moment for the complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$, probably arise due to strong distortion of octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} as it contains two non-equivalent ligands i.e. N,N-chelator and S,S-chelator. It is also evident from the fact that the reaction of $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$ with mono-dentate heterocyclic nitrogen donors yielded products in which one dan molecule is replaced by two mono-dentate nitrogen donors.

Electronic spectra :

The diffuse reflectance spectra of complexes show three bands in the region 9597–12048, 13928–18868 and 23697–25907 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ respectively suggesting octahedral coordination around Ni^{II} in these complexes. The ν_1 bands in these complexes are weak absorption bands suggesting distortion in octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} . The splitting of ν_2 bands in some of complexes have been found which may arise due to spin orbit coupling that mixes ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and 1E_g states, which are very close in energy at the Δ_0 value given by the ligands present in the mixed ligand complexes³⁸. The electronic spectra of complexes were also recorded in DMF solution to get behaviour of these mixed ligand complexes in solution and observed bands also suggest distorted octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II} ion in these complexes.

Infrared spectra of ligand and complexes :

The infrared spectra of mixed ligand complexes have been discussed in the light of earlier investigations^{1,39-45} on transition and non-transition metal dithiolates. The CED^{2-} ligand ion may be represented by resonating structure in its complexes as shown in Fig. 1.

The $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ band appearing at 2190 cm^{-1} in $\text{K}_2\text{CED}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is observed in the range 2195–2199 cm^{-1} in its mixed ligand complexes. The positive shifts in $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ band in complexes suggest non-involvement of nitrile group of CED^{2-} ion in bonding. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching band of ester group in these compounds appears as strong band in the region 1615–1628 cm^{-1} , which is indicative of delocalisation of C=O group with adjacent C=C band. The appearance of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ frequency in these mixed ligand complexes in almost same region as compared for $\text{K}_2\text{CED}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suggests that carbonyl oxygen is not participating in bonding. These complexes exhibit three strong

Fig. 1. Resonance forms of CED complexes.

to very strong bands in the regions 1369–1386, 1020–1042 and 930–984 cm^{-1} assignable ν_1 [$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$], ν_4 [$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{=CS}_2)$] and ν_2 [$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{=CS}_2)$] vibrations of $\text{C}=\text{CS}_2$ structure which were found in $\text{K}_2\text{CED}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 1320, 1020 and 930 cm^{-1} respectively^{16,39}. The positive shifts in $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ bands suggest that resonance form (a) (Fig. 1) is more dominant in 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate complexes. The presence of a single weak to medium band in the region 930–984 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ in these complexes indicate symmetrical bonding of both the sulphur atoms of the CED^{2-} ligands to metal ion⁴⁴.

The free 1,8-diaminonaphthalene shows $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$, broad band in the region 3305–3417 cm^{-1} , $\delta_{\text{a}}(\text{NH}_2)$ at 1615, $\delta_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$ at 1582 and $\rho_{\text{r}}(\text{NH}_2)$ at 813 and 757 cm^{-1} . The negative shifts in $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$, a little positive shifts in $\delta_{\text{a}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\delta_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$ (less sensitive bands) and positive shift in $\rho_{\text{r}}(\text{NH}_2)$ (sensitive band) have been found in the IR spectra of mixed ligand complexes suggesting bi-dentate behaviour of 1,8-diaminonaphthalene in these complexes. Similar behaviour has been reported^{20–23} for Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes containing dan.

The mixed ligand complexes containing heterocyclic nitrogen donors show their characteristic bands indicating their presence in the mixed ligand complexes⁴⁵. It is important to note that $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ from CED^{2-} ion and $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ from dan have overlapping regions.

The non-ligand bands observed in the ranges 361–393 and 280–285 cm^{-1} in the spectra of mixed ligand complexes are tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ ⁴² and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ ⁴⁵ modes respectively.

Reactivity of the complex :

When $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$ complex was allowed to react with heterocyclic nitrogen bases such as py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic, yielded substitution product of the composi-

tion, $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})(\text{CED})\text{L}_2]\cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{L} = \text{py}$, $x = 8$; α -pic, $x = 2$; β -pic, $x = 2$; or γ -pic, $x = 8$]. The results suggest that the $[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$ complex was in strained distorted structure which was being released by replacing one molecule of dan by two molecules of mono-dentate heterocyclic nitrogen bases.

Experimental

Materials :

All the chemicals used in this study were obtained from E. Merck of GR grade or equivalent quality, α -, β - and γ -picolines were obtained from Aldrich chemical company. 1,8-Diaminonaphthalene was also purchased from Aldrich chemical company, USA while $\text{K}_2\text{CED}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by a known literature method³⁹.

Synthesis of complexes :

$[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_3](\text{CED})$ (1) :

1,8-Diaminonaphthalene (4.746 g, 30 mM) in ethanol (100 cm^3) solution was added with stirring to a 100 cm^3 ethanol solution containing hydrated nickel nitrate (2.91 g, 10 mM), which yielded wild purple solution and resulted buff coloured precipitate. The precipitate was filtered and washed with ethanol. The resulting precipitate was dissolved in 150 cm^3 hot water and cooled to room temperature and filtered. To this filtrate, 50 cm^3 aqueous solution of $\text{K}_2\text{CED}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.83 g, 10 mM) was added with stirring which yielded yellow colour precipitate. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed with water, alcohol, ether and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl_2 .

$[\text{Ni}(\text{dan})_2(\text{CED})]$ (2) :

A 10 cm^3 ethanol solution of 1,8-diaminonaphthalene (0.3164 g, 2 mM) was added with constant stirring to a 20 cm^3 aqueous solution containing hydrated nickel nitrate (0.291 g, 1 mM) yielding purple coloured precipitate, changing instantaneously to brandy colour on stir-

ring. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed with water, alcohol. The precipitate was further dissolved in 10 cm³ of water by heating and filtered. To this filtrate, 50 cm³ aqueous solution of K₂CED.H₂O (0.283 g, 1 mM) was added with stirring which yielded yellow coloured precipitate. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed with water, alcohol, ether and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂.

The attempt was made to synthesize Ni(dan)(CED) by mixing Ni(NO₃)₂.6H₂O, 1,8-diaminonaphthalene and K₂CED.H₂O in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio, but the product obtained was characterized as [Ni(dan)₂(CED)].

[Ni(dan)(CED)(py)₂].8H₂O (3) :

[Ni(dan)₂(CED)] (1.124 g, 2 mM) was dissolved in 50 cm³ of pyridine by adding in small portions with stirring which made almost all the sample soluble. Finally, it was filtered and filtrate was allowed to evaporate under natural condition. It yielded black microcrystalline product which was suction filtered, washed with ether several times and dried in open air.

[Ni(dan)(CED)(α-pic)₂].2H₂O (4) :

[Ni(dan)₂(CED)] (1.124 g, 2 mM) was dissolved in 50 cm³ of DMF and 6 cm³ α-picoline was added to it followed by stirring for 1 h. The solution was filtered which did not give any precipitate. The filtrate was kept in open air for several days which yielded black colour sticky product. It was separated from solution and washed with ether several times which converted it into powder. The precipitate thus obtained was dried in open air.

[Ni(dan)(CED)(β-pic)₂].2H₂O (5) :

The complex was prepared exactly following same method for synthesis of [Ni(dan)(CED)(α-pic)₂].2H₂O by using β-picoline in place of α-picoline.

[Ni(dan)(CED)(γ-pic)₂].8H₂O (6) :

The complex was obtained by same method used for synthesis of [Ni(dan)(CED)(py)₂].8H₂O by replacing pyridine with γ-picoline. The compound was found in black microcrystalline form.

Analysis of the complexes :

The complexes were analysed for nickel content using standard literature procedure⁴⁶. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO₄. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined micro-analytically on CE 440 Exeter, USA. The content of water molecules were determined by heating the samples for 4 h in an electric oven maintained at 110–180 °C and determining the loss of weight.

Physical measurements :

The molar conductance of milli-molar solutions of the complexes in DMF was measured using Systronics direct reading conductivity 304 with a dip-type cell with platinized electrodes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on Sherwood Scientific Magnetic Susceptibility Balance using CoHg(SCN)₄ as calibrant. The experimental magnetic susceptibility values have been corrected for diamagnetism by the procedures given by Figgis and Lewis⁴⁷ and Earrshaw⁴⁸. Infrared spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 100 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded on Shimadzu (UV-

Table 1. Analytical data, molar conductance and magnetic moment values of the complexes

Complex (Colour)	% yield, (Dec. temp. °C)	Found (Calcd.) %					Λ _M (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
		Ni	S	N	C	H		
[Ni(dan) ₃](CED) (1) (Yellow)	53 (160)	8.01 (8.14)	8.49 (8.89)	14.23 (13.60)	61.23 (61.67)	4.39 (4.89)	65.0	2.99
[Ni(dan) ₂ (CED)] (2) (Mid buff)	48 (176)	10.15 (10.43)	10.84 (11.40)	12.36 (12.45)	57.02 (57.66)	4.24 (4.48)	50.0	2.47
[Ni(dan)(CED).(py) ₂].8H ₂ O (3) (Black)	43 (>285)	7.92 (8.30)	8.76 (9.07)	9.63 (9.91)	45.09 (45.90)	5.48 (5.85)	30.0	3.11
[Ni(dan)(CED)(α-pic) ₂].2H ₂ O (4) (Black)	42 (>285)	9.01 (9.36)	10.02 (10.23)	10.96 (11.18)	55.10 (55.60)	5.02 (5.30)	38.0	2.87
[Ni(dan)(CED)(β-pic) ₂].2H ₂ O (5) (Black)	40 (>285)	9.02 (9.36)	9.85 (10.23)	10.85 (11.18)	55.20 (55.60)	5.10 (5.30)	49.0	2.89
[Ni(dan)(CED)(γ-pic) ₂].8H ₂ O (6) (Black)	41 (>285)	7.94 (8.30)	8.95 (9.07)	9.76 (9.91)	45.62 (45.90)	5.42 (5.85)	30.0	2.88

Table 2. Electronic spectral data for the complexes

Complex	λ_{\max} (nm) (solid state)	λ_{\max} (nm) (in DMF solution)
[Ni(dan) ₃](CED) (1)	932, 628, 418	938, 809, 579, 419
[Ni(dan) ₂ (CED)] (2)	910, 692, 609, 422	804, 615, 534
[Ni(dan)(CED)(py) ₂].8H ₂ O (3)	860, 718, 386	840, 708, 420
[Ni(dan)(CED)(α -pic) ₂].2H ₂ O (4)	906, 530, 421	932, 534, 428
[Ni(dan)(CED)(β -pic) ₂].2H ₂ O (5)	830, 649, 534	984, 687, 537
[Ni(dan)(CED)(γ -pic) ₂].8H ₂ O (6)	1042, 685, 504, 396	982, 675, 540

Table 3. Characteristic IR bands (cm⁻¹) for the complexes

Complex	$\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ + $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(=\text{CS}_2)$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\rho_r(\text{NH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{S})$
[Ni(dan) ₃](CED) (1)	2195s	1615vs, 1586vs	1386vs	1400vs	1029m	932w	818s, 762vs	396w	–
[Ni(dan) ₂ (CED)] (2)	2196vs	1617vs, 1586vs	1385vs	1400vs	1029s	930w	819s, 762vs	393w	282w
[Ni(dan)(CED)(py) ₂].8H ₂ O (3)	2198s	1628vs, 1585vs	1369s	1446m	1042s	984w	817s, 760vs	373w	285w
[Ni(dan)(CED)(α -pic) ₂].2H ₂ O (4)	2197s	1627vs, 1596vs	1370s	1464s	1021s	984w	816s, 762vs	369w	283w
[Ni(dan)(CED)(β -pic) ₂].2H ₂ O (5)	2197s	1628vs, 1594vs	1384s	1463s	1022s	984w	816s, 763s	361w	281w
[Ni(dan)(CED)(γ -pic) ₂].8H ₂ O (6)	2199s	1624vs, 1595vs	1384s	1446s	1020s	984w	813s, 761s	373w	280w

v = very, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

1800) UV/Vis spectrophotometer. Analytical data together with colour, yield, magnetic moments and molar conductance values for mixed ligand complexes are presented in Table 1. The electronic and infrared spectral data for mixed ligand complexes are presented in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively.

Conclusions

Based on stoichiometry, magnetic and spectroscopic studies, distorted octahedral structure around nickel(II) in these complexes have been proposed. The ligand CED²⁻ and dan have been proposed to show their bi-dentate chelating behaviour and heterocyclic nitrogen donors as mono-dentate in these mixed ligand complexes. The reaction of [Ni(dan)₂(CED)] with heterocyclic nitrogen donors yielded substitution product in which one dan ligand has been replaced by two mono-dentate heterocyclic nitrogen donor. This observation suggest that the octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II} in [Ni(dan)₂(CED)] complex was distorted and strain was released when it was allowed to interact with mono-dentate heterocyclic nitrogen donor.

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